

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

NATIONAL CRITICAL REALISM OF AZERBAIJAN AND CLASSICAL LITERARY HERITAGE RELATIONS

Gasimov R.

*Doctor of philosophy (Ph.D) on philology, associate-professor
Nakhchivan Branch of The Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

The article elaborates the relationships between national critical realism and classical literary heritage. Analyzing the study profoundly, it has been revealed that progressive tradition and thought system of the classical heritage as a literary movement fed critical realism. The second issue to study in the article is the issue "Content". It has been noted that Nasimi's ideas, pathos, and determination manifested themselves in the great democrat writer J. Mammadguluzade in XX century. Critical notes by J. Mammadguluzadeh, M. A. Sabir, A. Nazmin, A. Hagverdiyev, M. Mojuz have been mentioned in the research. The article underlines that a national critical thinking system has existed in all periods, and it has been the foundation and stimulus for the existence of national development. Folk literature and written literature, as a unified system of national literary thought, have expressed critical thought in various forms, carried it into the future and served as a means for the development of national thinking.

Keywords: critical realism, literary heritage, classical period, cultural heritage, Nizami, Nasimi.

As it is known, Azerbaijani national critical realism has creatively used the traditions and opportunities of classical written literary heritage together with oral folklore traditions. Scholars commenting on the issue of Azerbaijani critical realism and classical heritage rightly say that "Molla Nasreddin magazine was closely connected not only with the oral art of the people to which it belonged, but also with the classical written literature" [6, p. 18]. M. Jalal [8], I. Agayev [1], I. Habibbeyli [4;5] and other scientists definitely talked about this. F.Huseynov wrote on the example of J.Mammadguluzadeh that: "He (J. Mammadguluzadeh - R.G.) also approached and appreciated the classics from the point of view of modernity" [6, p. 17].

A. Mirahmadov, who conducts research on the issue, said: "What and how have to take from the cultural heritage?" Everything that will be useful for the people in the destruction of the old society and the establishment of a new society! In each of the classics, one or more useful aspects attracted more attention. ...For example; Nizami, Khagani, Nasimi's humanism, ... Saadi and Hafiz's wise philosophy of life, Fuzuli, ... Akhundov and Melkum Khan's critique of medieval feudal lordship and colonial oppression" [7, p. 76], - he wrote. As the reason for the emergence of all these conclusions in the researches, the article "Fuzuli" written by prominent critical realist writer Jalil Mammadguluzadeh in 1925 was considered as the reason for the emergence of all these conclusions. In the same article, the great writer J. Mammadguluzadeh wrote in the "Molla Nasreddin" magazine, in other words, clarifying the participation of Molla Nasreddinism and the critical realist method and the place of the classical literary heritage in his example: "...the late Fuzuli started from the first issue of "Molla Nasreddin, until today, he participated in our collection and wrote poems. ... Now that "Molla Nasreddin" has started, no, ... Fuzuli is working in our collection... If you don't believe me, take the 20 years of "Molla Nasreddin" collections in front of you. If you look at any poem, you will see that there is a salt

from Fuzuli in it" and so on. [9, p. 247]. The great master J. Mammadguluzadeh skillfully connected the connections between Fuzuli traditions and the modern literary process with great mastery, calling the direction of creativity to which he belongs "mazachi" and putting forward ideas about the existence of this tradition in Fuzuli, the Fuzuli period and before that. In our opinion, the master writer is not only Fuzuli, but by saying "Fuzulies" he looked at the literary development and traditions that define Fuzuli's literary power and magic, and evaluated not only written literature, but also oral literature in the context of the traditions of a single folk literature, evaluation in the context of a single folk creativity and thought. by carrying out, he decisively concluded that his lines also skillfully benefited from these two branches and were the continuation of these traditions.

In general, critical realism benefited significantly from the progressive tradition and thought system of the classical heritage as a literary movement that carried out social construction and reformation. In general, by summarizing the studies carried out so far, we can say that critical realism, including Azerbaijani critical realism, turned benefiting from the progressive traditions of previous literary experience into a literary principle. Form and content relations were the main thing in relations of Azerbaijani critical realists with classical heritage. In terms of form, critical realists skillfully benefited from the classical heritage of verse and verse images. M.A.Sabir, A.Nazmi, A. Gamkusar, M. Mojuz, M.S.Ordubadı and others, especially J. Mammadguluzadeh, widely used ghazal, masnavi, quatrain, pentacle, hexameter and other genres of classical poetry. Even votive or parodies were popular with critical realists.

Of course, the second important issue was the issue of content. However, we are not going to repeat the ideas of the studies conducted in this matter. Because in the conducted studies, the idea was that the main theme in classical literature was the "rose-nightingale" theme and problem, and critical realists fought to get rid of this content. It is true that in the classical heritage,

the main images (not themes! - R.G.) consisted of the images of the nightingale, i.e. the lover and the lover. However, in our opinion, it did not always express love in the usual sense. Here, within the old form, new, important topics and problems could also be expressed. Both Nizami Ganjavi, Nasimi, and Fuzuli brought up completely new, humane, actual issues within the possibilities of the old form, and were able to contain serious problems. Classicists such as Nizami, Nasimi, Fuzuli were able to present their new human concepts and ideas precisely in these forms. Nasimi's serious rebellious pathos, calling for self-awareness, invitation to perfection were reflected in these forms. Therefore, it would not be correct to think that the classical heritage is always about ordinary love. Although literary studies serving the Soviet ideology think this way, even J. Mammadguluzadeh himself does not think this way and he considered Fuzuli as a powerful artist who wrote with the greatest mastery [9]. Their struggle was to seriously criticize the imitative "literary clowns" who imitate the classical heritage and do not contain any important aesthetic ideals, ideas and problems, and to come out with the demand to treat literature with responsibility like Fuzuli. In this respect, we must say that critical realism, which actually found its existence in the form of a strong movement at the beginning of the 20th century, did not differ at all from Nizami, Nasimi, and Fuzuli in terms of ideas and content. The issue of humanism, which is the main content-problem of Azerbaijani critical realism defined at the beginning of the 20th century, gained a new content by transferring it from the classical heritage. The rights of man, moral freedom, the fact that education and science are only for man, and the demand to always improve one's conditions, as expressed in the classical heritage, critical realists also appear with these ideas, they tackle the human problem with all its social content, human freedom, they turned issues such as the right into the main problem of fiction, conducted their own literary struggles, and in this respect showed unity with the literary problems and ideas of the classical heritage. The pathetic phrase "They said goods to goods, man to man" summarizes the humanistic character and theoretical principle of Azerbaijani critical realism, the artistic appeal "I have told you, O my Muslim brothers" expressed the main essence, the main content of the formation and struggle of Azerbaijani critical realism.

Nasimi's ideas, pathos, and determination manifested themselves in the great democrat writer J. Mammadguluzadeh in the 20th century. M.A.Sabir, who escaped from the teaching of critical realism, found his embodiment as the face of Nasimi at the beginning of the 20th century with all his soul, talent and pathos. Following these thoughts, we would like to add that "Molla Nasreddin"'s "humour" style, critical thinking, as the great Mirza Jalil himself said, was closely and directly connected with the traditions of Fuzuli and Azerbaijani literature in general, even the logical result of previous traditions and its appeared as a sequel. So, in our opinion, the concept of "critical", which includes the concepts of "reformism, awakening and humanism" in itself, has had its own history in all eras. Joining Nabi Ozdemir's opinion and even making additions, we can

say that Mevlana, Yunus Emre and Fuzuli (as well as Imadaddin Nasimi and others. In fact, Nasimi is a symbol of "mind" with all the pathos of creativity! -R.G.) "heart", Molla Nasreddin "mind" as a symbol, they express the expression of "mind-heart" unity, which is the foundation of Turkish folk philosophy. The main issue that carries Molla Nasreddin from the past to the future is this wholeness [18]. In other words, in Molla Nasreddin, the wisdom of simple people's sages, critical laughter, style of mockery, mockery and sarcasm, people's concerns, pain, problems, Nasimi's philosophy together with courage, trust and confidence in man and his greatness, Fuzuli's love, affection, innocence, sadness, others' suffering, Dede Gorgud's seniority, trust, trust, respect, etc. There was a. Molla Nasreddin, from every profession, class, class, and side, united all kinds of differences in his hero type and personality, representing a common social identity and thought. Based on the studies of Abdurrahman Gozal [17], we can say with full determination that Molla Nasreddin created the peak of Turkish critical thinking and philosophy by combining the "guidance" before him in his critical thinking and wisdom. Even in Molla Nasreddin's anecdotes, it can be clearly observed that the philosophy of guidance before him has the tradition of "realistic understanding of the truth" and "critical review of divine expressions". A. Gozal wrote that Molla Nasreddin was a "guardian" who revealed a critical attitude by combining criticism and guidance terminology [17]. From this point of view, it can be thought that Jalil Mammadguluzadeh was immortalized as the first and only artist and folk sage who correctly evaluated these qualities and characteristics of Molla Nasreddin's wisdom and continued it in the 20th century with its full meaning. In addition, critical realists in Azerbaijani literature gathered in the press agency "Molla Nasreddin" and defined the literary teaching of Molla Nasreddinism.

We can definitely say that it would be more correct and logical to look for the true historical root of the artistic quality of folk laughter, humor and meza style, which was successfully transferred to the 20th century and became the artistic method and method of reflection of Azerbaijani critical realism, in the classical heritage, in the same or close period of Molla Nasreddin. It is from this point of view that the emergence, conditions of emergence, socio-historical environment, content, rock and philosophy, main slogans, etc. from the point of view, it is possible to connect and compare Azerbaijan's national critical realism with the philosophical trend of Hurufism. Mostly because the participants of this philosophical training and the critical realists of the 20th century were closer to each other in terms of their fighting spirit, method and ideas. That is why both the scribes and the critical realists saw man as "perfect and ignorant" and announced the time to separate man and animal from each other. The mission of awakening people and society was an important goal of both trainings. These two teachings were closely connected with each other in different periods, a call to people who are far from the truth, who have lost their true face and essence, who live a false life, and act. Imadaddin Nasimi's words, "Hey unaware of yourself,

wake up! Come to the truth, who is not true, lie, wake up!" [13, p. 293], or "You have already lost the jami-Jamshid, wake up, hey heedless" [13, p. 106] verses, as the thoughts of a great humanist poet calling people to wake up, perform exactly the same content and essence as the awakening mission of critical realism. Or the great humanitarian poet "Hey bulbuli-gudsi (nightingale), what a mysterious cage you are, break the cage, demand fresh flowers!" [14, p.49] as a call to the mission of changing and renewing the social environment, conditions, and thought of the person, is united in the same action and purpose with the leading slogans of the critical realism of the 20th century, such as "it is necessary to draw a pen over the old, create a new life" [9], thus, it manifests itself as the awakening mission of literature. From this point of view, it is possible to clearly see a certain idea-content connection between the philosophical teaching of Hurufism [in our opinion, the sequence of manifestation of the philosophical movement of Hurufism in fiction should be called humanism literary trend in Azerbaijani literature - R.G.] and the critical realism of the 20th century.

If we pay attention, it is possible to see close connections between the creative problems of other prominent literary figures of the Middle Ages, characterized as the period of critical-ideological development and renaissance, and the literary problems of the 20th century critical realism. Even the great heart poet Fuzuli's ghazal criticizing religious figures who are devoid of consciousness and thought, deed and goodness, and the combination of the idea contained in it with the subject-problem circle of the 20th century critical realists, cannot but cause surprise.

My heart, try never trample on prayer rug,
Never believe the prayers, never be with them! [12, p. 284]

We can say that Fuzuli criticizes the false religious figures who wear the dress of a believer and engage in false deeds. Literary studies have definitely noted that critical realists of Azerbaijan also played a major role in their works and literary teachings, where they criticized and exposed the religious people who came out of false deeds in the guise of a believer. Criticism of false religious figures and false religious rulings, reformation of religious rulings and adaptation to the modern era were important as one of the literary-theoretical issues of Azerbaijani critical realism. Various Gazi, Molla, Zahid and other characters and actions exposed to the lens of artistic criticism in critical realist literature were a kind of "complaint" of critical realist literature. It was not accidental that Azerbaijani critical realists saw religious institutions and religious ignorance more than political structures as the main cause of social backwardness and national inertia. Fuzulin's poem, which regrettably noted that religious centers have become more centers of ignorance, was clearly expressed in the analyzed poem.

In the ghazal, "Bow down and prostrate, do not drop the crown of peace on your head", "Don't listen to the muezzin's wail, don't be alarmed", "The power of the crowd in the mosque, according to the power, please, don't increase even one power!", "Fuzuli, obedience does not bear fruit, what is your attempt" [12, p.

Verses like 284] attract attention in terms of their meaning and content.

Although the first verse of Fuzuli's mentioned ghazal expresses a general, introductory idea, already in the second verse, "Bend down in prostration, never drop the crown of freedom from your head", belief in the greatness of man and love were in the foreground. Here, as in the letters, the supremacy of the person who carries the majesty of God, his dignity, the majesty - alif (as "alif" in the Arabic alphabet is the first and most important letter of the word God), which also expresses the majesty and inflexibility of man (the first letter of the word Adam is alif), it was a letter that also expressed loftiness and inflexibility and became his symbol - R.G.) is glorified and satisfied, and the protest against the breaking of that lofty determination by prostration finds its place. If a person carries the dignity of God and a part of it, why should a person lower this greatness by prostrating? Because by bowing, a person also becomes a means for bowing down and prostrating the high God that he carries in his soul. Therefore, prostration is not suitable for human-God unity. The verse "Don't listen to the wail of Muezzin, don't be alarmed" clearly shows that a perfect person knows the meaning and essence of death, life, good, evil, bitter, sweet, light, and darkness. Why should a person who carries goodness, light, perfection, and love in his thoughts be alarmed by the death and the fear of suffering in the muezzin's wail? God has such a flawless image and beauty that we should talk about him with love, not fear him, and connect with him. Death is not sadness, it is the death that brings a person to his beloved, to his lover, to the most perfect of beauties - God, who is high and flawless, brings him to his unity, leads him to the valley of love, becomes a means to his perfection. "The powers that brought the crowd into the mosque, according to the power, please do not increase one power!", Fuzuli said, that people who do not carry perfection in themselves carry hatred, power and hatred to the mosque, doubts and discord in the bonds of unity and love of the almighty God. regrets what they brought. "Don't think the imam is intelligent, don't entrust your authority to him," says the poet, protesting that imams, that is, religious leaders, are not intelligent at all and do not fulfill the verses of God with full meaning and faith. The poet Fuzuli, who has great faith, considers imperfect obedience to be fruitless by saying: "Fuzuli, disobedient obedience does not bear fruit, what are you trying to do?"

As it can be seen, the ghazal is dominated by the spirit of criticizing a person - a pious, worshipful person. It is as if the ghazal suggests this idea that "when everyone considers himself perfect, pious, faithful and confident, he looks at himself with critical eyes, if he makes a clean and rotten one, he will see his faults and shortcomings." In this regard, prof. Y.Babayev wrote that: "Following what the Shari'a dictates mainly includes external rules. A person can make mistakes and fall short on this path. Because an external action that is not completed with inner faith remains formal and can lead to error. Therefore, if the execution of sharia's rulings and rules is of a formal nature, if it is not transformed from outward action into inner belief, inner

love, and a factor of spiritual perfection, then this kind of piety is considered defective in knowledge" [2, p. 34-35].

When mentioning these ideas, we definitely remember the critical notes of J. Mammadguluzadeh, M. A. Sabir, A. Nazmin, A. Hagverdiyev, M. Mojuz, and generally false and opportunistic religious figures according to the teaching of critical realists. Of course, critical realists also demanded the right faith and action from a person, as it was said before, religious denial and rejection had no place, worship based on actions and results was considered correct. It would be logical and correct to understand and explain the struggle of critical realists with religious fanaticism and ignorance in this way. The evil deeds of Gazi in "Stories of Danabash Village" that turned religious rules into a source of profit were combined with the satirical pathos of Sabir "Zahida, let's take off our clothes once, let's get out of our inner thoughts", and the religious management of Azerbaijani critical realism was defined as the principle of reform and criticism of false religious figures. Such a spirit of criticism prevails in M.Fuzuli's famous "Letter to Nishanchi Pasha" called "Written complaint", where the famous "I gave a greeting and they did not accept it because it is not a bribe" etc. other numerous ideas are considered the most perfect examples of the period, and Fuzuli's critical views in particular. There were even those who observed the "satirical spirit" in this work [10, p.76].

By the way, it is possible to observe such critical spirit and judgments more clearly in the work "Hidayatil-ikhvan" by Nematullah Nakhchivani, a great scholar of religion of the 15th-16th centuries. "In Hidayatul-ikhwan treatise, which can be considered an example of sufi criticism, Nakhchivani criticized philosophers and theologians on the issues of vujud (existence), wajib-ul-vujud, marifatullah and ruyatullah, taking into account their attitude to the subject of reason" [15, p.8]. Nakhchivani even popularized the critical thinking, "together with rhetoricians and philosophers, he severely criticized the "sheikhdom seekers" in order to earn a living without "following the right path", turn trade, multiply subjects, and gain wealth and trust among the common people" [15, p. 8]. For Nematullah Nakhchivani, people are "in two parts, being a scientist and an ignorant person. A scientist is veiled from God by reason. The mind is a close veil. The ignorant person is veiled from him by his enthusiasm" [15, p. 57]. Nakhchivani also expressed his agreement with the scribes on the issue of the perfect human being, saying, "The Creator (The God) turned what he took from the kneaded mud into a moderate body, shaped the statue without giving it a soul, and then breathed out his soul. ...man became alive with a blown spirit. Then this man was accepted as a sajdag to the community of angels and the "ayn" of all created things. Thus, man became the "ayn" of the "ayn". For this reason, it is named with the word "man" [15, p. 67]. Nakhchivani, like the scribes before him, said, "Everybody should use his gifted mind from God" [15, p. 72], by providing rational understanding with the use of reason, "to discover secrets for himself" [15, p. 72], " According to

his innate talent, he must ensure and realize the discovery of God" [15, p. 72]. Nakhchivani: "Those who claim guidance without being aware of the right path, the temple and the quality of Ma'ad are only servants of the devil. He tempts people, they take the words of the people of the right path and attribute them to them without realizing it. How can these weaklings understand, on the contrary, their goals from acting as sheikhs are to make a living, convert trade, multiply subjects, ... gain wealth and trust among the public" [15, p. 73], seriously criticizing the opportunistic and profit-seeking clerics and reprimanded, but also explained and explained the reasons for the emergence of false beliefs, false customs, unnecessary worship, superstition and superstition among the common people. Although this example is not actually the material of fiction, it clearly shows that even in the Middle Ages those who falsified their religious duties were severely criticized and punished. Those who are responsible for the proper fulfillment of the social duty of religion have been held responsible and brought to the attention of criticism. From this point of view, critical realism, which legalized the transformation of critical thinking into an artistic method at the beginning of the 20th century, at a time when national self-determination and awakening were relevant, looked at social shortcomings, as well as the field of religion and Sharia, with a more open eye, and came up with reformative ideas in order to put everything in its right place. In this regard, the criticism of opportunistic religious figures was seriously criticized in J. Mammadguluzadeh's story "Danabash kandinin ahvalatlari (Stories of Danabash village)", the tragicomedies "Oluler (The Dead)", " Deli yiginjagi (Assembly of Madmen)" , A. Hagverdiyev's ""Mozalan beyin seyahetnamesi (Mozalan bey's Travelogue)", and Y.V. Chamanzaminli's "Jennetin qebzi (Receipt of Paradise)". The works of Azerbaijani critical realists such as J. Mammadguluzadeh, M. A. Sabir, A. Nazmi, A. Gamkusar, M. S. Ordubadi, M. A. Mojuz, etc. are dedicated to the criticism of the disfigurements and forgeries of religious figures in the name of religion and sharia.

Thus, as you follow the entire history of literature, you are sure that a national critical thinking system has existed in all periods, and it has been the foundation and stimulus for the existence of national development. Folk literature and written literature, as a unified system of national literary thought, have expressed critical thought in various forms, carried it into the future and served as a means for the development of national thinking. In general, the research fully proves that the criticism in fiction has stimulated the awakening of national consciousness, self-awareness and the process of self-correction, thus becoming the basis for solving issues such as independence and development. In this sense, the critical realism of the 20th century greatly benefited from the classical literary heritage. Because one of the important sources that reflects, revives and develops the national critical thinking system is written literature. In this regard, mainly J. Mammadguluzadeh, M. Sabir, A. Nazmi, A. Qamkusar, M. Ordubadi, M. Mojuz and others. it is possible to "find some salt" [9] in the works of critical realist artists from the art of

great classical masters, from the traditions of the critical thinking system in general.

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